

AFRICAN FEMININITY AND THE TRAJECTORY OF LOVE AND VIOLENCE: CONTEMPORARY REALITIES AND RESPONSES IN SELECTED AFRICAN NOVELS

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*The authors declare
that no funding was
received for this work.*

Received: 20-July-2025

Accepted: 01-March-2026

Published: 28-April-2026

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This article is published in the **MSI Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (MSIJMR)** ISSN 3049-0669 (Online)

The journal is managed and published by MSI Publishers.

Volume: 3, Issue: 4 (April-2026)

ABSTRACT: World cultures and their peoples have undergone diverse schisms which directly and indirectly challenge and upset the systems, and wreck the economies of many families, groups and nations. These developments have consequently imposed profound concerns, or intensified previous ones on governments, non-governmental agencies, groups and individuals, and have opened up a vista of reactions, many of which are of literary significance. A major form of reaction is violence. This paper is interested in the actions that constitute violence that women react against. It is also curious about the forms of women's responses. Accordingly, the paper focuses on the applicability of the different perceptions of violence that are depicted in African literature, and specifically examines how femininity is affected by violence within the context of love, as well as the various reactions of the subject/victim. Deploying the qualitative methodology to appraise femininity at the convergence of love and violence, or violence-in-love, as captured in Nawal El Saadawi's *Woman at Point Zero*, Ama Ata Aidoo's *Changes: A Love Story*, and Chimamanda Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus*, the study establishes that the contemporary woman, unlike her foremothers, is equipped

with the strategies as well as appropriate dispositions and the determination to take action, thereby debunking the age-long perceptions of African femininity as passive, weak, docile, willingly subservient and manipulable.

Keywords: *Femininity, Violence, Love, Realities and Responses*

**AFRICAN FEMININITY AND THE TRAJECTORY OF LOVE AND VIOLENCE:
CONTEMPORARY REALITIES AND RESPONSES
IN SELECTED AFRICAN FEMALE WRITINGS**

Conceptual Clarifications

When Allan G. Johnson asserted in *The Gender Knot: Unraveling Out Patriarchal Legacy* that "...femininity applies only to women's place in heterosexual relationships. ... In characteristic patriarchal style, the entirety of women's being is reduced to their ties with men, particularly lovers and husbands" (63), he implied that femininity is most suitably situated within the context that guarantees the binary structure of femininity and masculinity. This means that femininity and masculinity should be mutually self-authenticating as a way of creating a balance for the operations of the genders; and for the focus of this study, this mutuality is envisioned for the micro level. It is natural to conceive femininity as an aspect of the binarism that involves masculinity, and also recognize the notions that are attributed to each of both of them.

Since femininity refers to the nature of being female, this paper conceptualizes femininity as referring to the woman, to womanhood, to womanliness and the like. Accordingly, Betty Friedan states that femininity entails "... menstrual difficulties, sexual frigidity, promiscuity, pregnancy fears, childbirth depression, the high incidence of emotional breakdown and suicide ..." (32). And Sigmund Freud defines it as a "preference for passive aims, or ... the active pursuit of a passive function" (115). As contestable as Freud's claim here is, it is obvious that femininity offers a broad spectrum within which to situate the discourse on the experiences of the female in the context of love. It is, therefore, significant that the notions of femininity in most cultures of the world are similar as they project antithetical views of the

ubiquitous acclaimed natural masculine inclination to domination, adventure, courage, control, aggression and heroism. Femininity is conceived as the opposite of all the masculine traits. Diverse cultures perceive it to imply weakness, passivity, care, nurturance, intuitive, gentleness, emotive and modesty. These characteristics have been deployed by many artists in the portraiture of feminine characters and images.

Essentially, as the emphasis of this study is specifically on African femininity, it is pertinent to appraise the African conception of femininity. In Africa, femininity is best appreciated within the paradigm of patriarchy. Though the standard notions of femininity above apply in the Africa context, in addition are such characteristics as silence and the leitmotif of failure. In fact, it is often a phenomenon of shame, denigration and derision. Angela Fubara (103) explains that “a non-achiever or a failure is regarded as a woman epitomized by Okonkwo’s father, Unoka who is called ‘Agbala’, depicting an effeminate figure who had neither titles nor barns of yams. Osugo in that same category is disgraced out of a meeting by Okonkwo, the achiever, who tells Osugo scornfully and derogatorily that ‘this meeting is for men’ (*Things Fall Apart* 11).

Femininity and Patriarchy

In general terms, patriarchy defines what African femininity entails, and also evolves a pivot around which matters that relate to femininity revolve in the private and public spheres. The stipulations that determine what femininity entails and the expectations for it in the family and the society are typically patriarchal. This implies that patriarchy conditions the female all through her life to operate with feelings of inadequacy, dependence on the male and limited access to resources that would facilitate an impactful life. Indeed, a tendency toward the reification of the female makes her more often a sexual object than a person. This is particularly so when she is denied human rights through chattel status. Even where this has been partly amended the cumulative effect of religion and custom is still very powerful and has enormous psychological consequences (Friedan 54). This is because the fundamental patriarchal impulse connects the woman with sex and misdeed, misdemeanor, wrongdoing or sin. This implies, as Friedan highlights, that the “large quantity of

guilt attached to sexuality in patriarchy is overwhelmingly placed upon the female, who is, culturally speaking, held to be the culpable or the more culpable party in nearly any sexual liaison, whatever the extenuating circumstances” (54).

From infancy, through adolescence to adulthood, the female is made to believe that she is not as complete as her male counterpart to perform certain roles. Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie recounts how as a young girl in elementary school in Nsukka, the main criterion for becoming a class monitor is to obtain the highest score in the class test. Chimamanda scores the highest in the class, and according to her, “... to my surprise, my teacher said the monitor had to be a boy. She [the teacher] had forgotten to make that clear earlier; she assumed it was obvious. A boy had the second highest score on the test. And he would be monitor” (*We Should All be Feminists* 12). Meanwhile, the boy is not ambitious in any way to be the class monitor, but because Chimamanda is female, she is denied that right even though she has met the requirement. This is a manifestation of femininity: the male is often preferred to the female, even if he is a second-rate performer, and that is how the young girl is habituated to accept whatever treatment she is accorded, while her male counterpart is treated with dignity, and allowed considerable latitude to represent himself and make choices.

The trend of circumscribing the horizon of the girl child’s physical operations as well as the scope of her mental performance progresses into adulthood, and affects her activities in the family and society. In the evaluation of the role of patriarchy in the anatomizing of femininity, this study identifies the centrality of the institution of marriage which is also widely regarded as the epitome of the expression of love, and the demonstration of affection in any heterosexual relationship. For the African woman, marriage or any intimate relationship constitutes a site of struggle for identity, personhood, voice, choice, recognition and humanity. The woman in such a relationship strives to resolve the contradiction that becomes particularly apparent between her sexual role and what she is capable and willing to do. Unfortunately, that the man, who is the woman’s intimate partner deploys violence as a means of control of the woman inhibits the possibility of evolving a *modus vivendi* between the forces of patriarchy and the passion that should underlie the relationship. These

issues set the framework for this paper to examine the woman in patriarchy, and in the heterosexual liaison – marriage and or casual relationships.

Prominently, the patriarchal form of heterosexuality is male-determined, male-centred and male-dominated, thus, its social signification transcends sexuality, and reflects male-supremacy, male-control, and male-aggression, which means that even in the expression of love, the man regards the woman as one that he must dominate and control, and this is sanctioned by the culture (and in some cases, religion). In explicating the basis for the relationship between love and violence in heterosexual liaisons, Nawal El Saadawi explains that “... most men cannot stand an experienced and intelligent woman. It would seem as though the man is afraid of her because of her capacity to understand him and see through his failures, or weaknesses ... She knows very well that his masculinity is not real, not an essential truth, but only an external shell, built up and imposed on women by societies based on class and sexual discrimination” (*The Hidden Face of Eve* 77). This is echoed by Hannah Arendt as she highlights the mutual exclusivity of violence and power. She argues against the patriarchal incongruity that identifies violence with power, implying that since the man is the accredited repository of power in every gender relationship, it means that he must be excused if he displays violence. According to her, “violence appears when power is in jeopardy, but left on its own course its end is the disappearance of power ... Violence can destroy power; it is utterly incapable of creating it” (34).

The pursuit of power by men through the oppression of women in the context of love illustrates male discomfiture, which is visible in every aspect of gender relationship, and Christina Sommers stresses that politics is essentially sexual and even the so-called democracies are male hegemonies (23). Whether the figure of authority is father, lover, husband, acquaintance or employer, the underlying principle is control, where control can also mean power, influence, predominance exploitation, superintendence, and authority. However, if it happens that the woman (or female partner or victim) in the heterosexual relationship reacts in ways that seek to protect her interest, or promote her image, then she is met with one form of violence or another. Within this dialectic is the validity of Barbara Omolade’s view that protecting women was the most significant measure of black manhood, and the

central aspect of black male patriarchy (13). Evidently, patriarchy ensconces a relationship of dominance and subordination within the romantic love *mise-en-scène*.

Violence in Heterosexual Relationships in the Selected Novels

This section appraises three African novels by African women from Egypt, Ghana and Nigeria. The selection is deliberate because by the spread, the conclusion of this study on contemporary African women would be fairly valid. The novels are *Woman at Point Zero* by Nawal El Saadawi, *Changes: A Love Story* by Ama Ata Aidoo, and *Purple Hibiscus* by Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie. Nawal El Saadawi's *Woman at Point Zero (Woman)* expounds the story of Firdaus who is raised by a "a poor peasant father, who could neither read nor write, [but] knew how to exchange his virgin daughter for a dowry [before she would get corrupted] ... [and] how to beat his wife and make her bite the dust each night (12). Unfortunately, Firdaus is orphaned as a young girl, and her uncle who is a teacher in Cairo, takes her from her parents' home to the city, Cairo, where she goes to school. She is fond of her uncle, and in him, she has a sense of hope for herself:

During the cold winter nights, I curled up in my uncle's arms like a baby in its womb. We drew warmth from our closeness. My face buried in his arms, I wanted to tell him that I loved him, but the words would not come. I wanted to cry but the tears would not flow ...

One day I fell sick with fever. My uncle sat on my bed by my side holding my head, patting me gently with his great long finger, and I slept all night holding on to his hand (21-22).

This is the warm filial passion that Firdaus enjoys with her uncle, who has adequately filled the gaps in her life from the loss of her parents from who she hardly enjoyed love or care. Unknown to her, the uncle transits to an unpropitious form of passion towards her. She recounts:

I was trembling all over, seized with a feeling I could not explain, that my uncle's great long fingers would draw close to me after a

little while, and cautiously lift the eiderdown under which I lay. Then his lips touch my face and press down on my mouth, and his trembling fingers would feel their way slowly upwards over my thighs (22).

This violation gets Firdaus to become sensitive about herself and the strange experiences that she has been having. Shortly afterwards, her uncle gets married, and he and his new wife get Firdaus, who is 18 years old, married off to Sheikh Mahmoud, a man of over 60 years old. He is repulsive in presentation and obnoxious in attitude, as Firdaus describes:

On his chin, below the lip, was a large swelling, with a hole in the middle. Some days the hole would be dry, but on others it would turn into a rusty old tap exuding drops red in colour like blood, or whitish yellow, like pus (43).

While Firdaus tries to get to terms with this revolting old personality, she finds that “he kept looking at my plate while I ate, and if I left anything over he picked it up, put it in his mouth and after swallowing, quickly told me off for my wastefulness. Yet I was not given to wasting anything, and the only food I left on the plate were the scanty remains which stuck to its surface, and could only be removed with soap and water. The Sheikh cannot contain Firdaus who he feels is wasteful, so he starts beating her:

One day he discovered some leftover scraps of food, and started yelling at me so loudly, that all the neighbours could hear. After that incident, he got into the habit of beating me whether he had a reason for it or not ... on one occasion, he hit me all over with his shoe. My face and body became swollen and bruised (44).

The main contradiction that confronts Firdaus from these experiences arises from her inability to reconcile the battery she suffers in a marriage with which she is trying to get to terms, with the personality of a supposedly pious Sheikh, who is a recognized religious leader, a man three decades older than her, and evidently older than her late father. Firdaus’s inability to harmonise the conflicting dynamics thus impels her to

leave the Sheikh and return to her uncle's house, but she is promptly returned to the Sheikh, and counseled that "the precepts of [the Muslim] religion permitted such punishment [of wife battery]. A virtuous woman was not supposed to complain about her husband. Her duty was perfect obedience" (44). Perhaps Firdaus's uncle and wife are abashed by Firdaus's strange response to her experience of battery, thus they insist that she must stay in the marriage and endure it. This confirms the fact that emotional reaction to violence against women in patriarchy is often peculiarly equivocal. Specifically, radical reactions to wife-battery often generate discomfort, amusement and shame. Firdaus fits into Judith Herman's observation that repeated trauma in childhood forms and deforms the personality, and that:

The child trapped in an abusive environment is faced with the formidable tasks of adaptation. She must find a way to preserve a sense of trust in people who are terrifyingly unpredictable, [and] powerful in a situation of helplessness. Unable to care for or protect herself, she must compensate for the failures of adult care and protection with the only means at her disposal, an immature system of psychological defenses (96).

Unfortunately, Firdaus seems ensnared in a marriage to an impregnable parsimonious old man who also physically assaults her. With sustained battery, she leaves the Sheikh again, and walks aimlessly rather than go again to her uncle's house.

Firdaus meets Bayoumi, a coffee shop operator, who takes her in to stay with him in his two-room apartment. Her insistence on using her secondary school certificate to find a job and gain financial empowerment seems to constitute an affront to Bayoumi who has been happy and satisfied with her roles of cooking their meals, and keeping the apartment clean. But Firdaus recognizes and agrees with Betty Friedan that "... education and the right to participate in the more advanced work of society were women's greatest needs" (335). In consequence, it is consistent that Firdaus desires to utilize her certificate to get a job and work. But that generates a twist in her relationship with Bayoumi as the initial cordiality and kindness from him fizzle out, and she recounts that "... he jumped up and slapped me on the face, saying ... you street walker, you low woman. His hand as big and strong, and it was the heaviest

slap I had ever received on my face ... (49). The next moment he hit me with his fist in the belly so hard that I lost consciousness immediately (50).

Bayoumi often disparages Firdaus as “slut, bitch”, and also insults her mother. He locks her into the house and goes out all day, and then gets her to be gang-raped. She eventually leaves Bayoumi, and walks the streets again, ends up in prostitution, then experiences diverse forms of exploitation in erotic relationships: she sleeps with a policeman who waives her arrest and refuses to pay her, implying that he has sex with her in lieu of the arrest that she deserves as a suspected prostitute. Within this context, this paper identifies the essence of Kate Millett’s analysis of Freud’s postulation on femininity and violence in love. She argues that “... for that vast majority of women who do not live on pedestals, Freud realizes it is psychologically necessary for men to debase them in prostitution and brutalized sexuality ...” which leads to the evolution of his 1912 treatise “The Most Prevalent Form of Degradation in Erotic Life” (197).

Evidently, Firdaus is aware that the law punishes women [prostitutes] like her, but turns a blind eye to what men do (92). She may easily be the sample described by Herman in:

The emotional state of the chronically abused child ranges from a baseline of unease, through intermediate states of anxiety and dysphoria, to extremes of panic, fury and despair. Not surprisingly a great many survivors develop chronic anxiety and depression which persist into adult life (108).

Of course, Firdaus has experienced diverse degrees of panic, fury and despair at different times from her childhood while growing up. They progressively intensify as she moves from one place to another in search of a convivial environment. Thus, when Marzouk, the pimp offers her an opportunity for an intimate relationship within which he would protect her, her sensibilities become alerted, and she is conscious that it could be a lure for another level of exploitation, violence and or battery: as he looks directly into her eyes, he tells her “You’re living an illusion. I can see in your eyes how love has broken the spirit that used to shine. You’ve never really known

what it is to be in love. I'm going to teach you" (93). But Firdaus declines as she declares that she does not "mix work with love" (93). This is a principle that enables Firdaus to note that love and work are mutually exclusive since love seems to be the domain in which the woman is the most vulnerable, yet her vulnerability becomes her Achilles heel. Marzouk attempts to take advantage of her, and she puts up a façade of the "passive, lifeless thing, yet refusing to surrender, undefeated. Its passivity was a form of resistance, a strange ability not to feel either pleasure or pain, not to let a single hair on ... [her] body, be moved (*Woman* 93-94). Robert Bly's position is significant that:

When we disentangle aggression and passivity, we can also see that although women tend not to be aggressive, they are far from passive. By casting women as passive, patriarchal culture promotes the fiction that women are essentially inactive (60).

That Firdaus stabs and kills Marzouk demonstrate the fact that though femininity is erroneously perceived as characterized by diffidence and timorousness, yet therein lie the pursuit of selfhood, immanent courage, and resoluteness for freedom.

Similar issues underlie Ama Ata Aidoo's *Changes: A Love Story* (*Changes*), which portrays Esi Sekyi, an Analyst in the Department of Urban Statistics. Her husband, Oko Sekyi, who teaches in a co-educational secondary school, is deeply in love with his wife, Esi, and often desires her. They have a 6-year old daughter, Ogyaanowa. While Oko wishes to have more children, or perhaps just one more, Esi shows no inclination for another child, and she is on contraceptives. Also, her ideas about motherhood are radical, and generate some curious questions as posed by Friedan in:

When motherhood, a fulfillment held sacred down the ages, is defined as a total way of life, must women themselves deny the world and the future open to them? Or does the denial of that world *force* them to make motherhood a total way of life? The line between mystique and reality dissolves; real women embody the split in the image (58) (Emphasis in original).

In fact, Esi applies the split between motherhood and career, and chooses to gear all her attention and energies to her career. The omniscient narrator explains that “Esi definitely put her career well above any duties she owed as a wife. She was a great cook, who complained endlessly any time she had to enter the kitchen. Their home was generally run by an elderly house help, whom they both called ‘Madam’ behind her back (8). Betty Friedan advances the argument that “women who do not look for jobs equal to their actual capacity, who do not let themselves develop the lifetime interests and goals which require serious education and training, who take a job ... to ‘help out at home’ or just to kill extra time, are walking, almost as surely as the ones who stay inside the housewife trap, to a nonexistent future (344). By implication, if a job is to serve as an escape route from the trap for the woman, it is only right that she approaches the job with utmost seriousness, and regards it as “part of a life plan, [as] work in which she can grow as part of society” (Friedan 345).

Evidently, Esi’s priority is at variance with her husband’s values concerning work, the family and vision of life in general. He usually tries to gain his wife’s attention, but she is constantly preoccupied with her professional activities: she garners tremendous respect from her colleagues and other people because of her competence and penchant for high performance. She is consistent in her professionalism, “leaving the house virtually at dawn; returning home at dusk; often bringing work home? Then there were all those conferences. Geneva, Addis, Dakar one half of the year; Rome, Lusaka, Lagos the other half (8).

By the lifestyle described above, Esi Sekyi deals with Friedan’s notion as expressed in *The Feminine Mystique* that “the major problem of modern women is how to respond to the voice that constantly states ‘I want something more than my husband and my children and my house’, which Friedan identifies as ‘the problem that has no name’” (32). Interestingly, one morning as Esi is preparing for work, Oko can no longer resist her. In a clear dramatic twist, he forces her into love making. The omniscient narrator describes:

... Oko flung the bed cloth away from him, sat up, pulled her down, and moved on her. Esi started to protest. But he went on doing what he had determined to do all morning. He squeezed her breast repeatedly, thrust his

tongue into her mouth, forced her unwilling legs apart, entered her, plunging in and out of her, thrashing to the left, to the right, all over. Breathing like a marathon runner at the end of a particularly grueling race, he got off her, and fell heavily back on his side of the bed. He tried to draw the bed cloth to cover both of them ... (9).

Oko is remorseful after this act of violation on his wife, but he would not express it because as a man, he recognizes and upholds the patriarchal argument that “sex is something a husband claims from his wife as his right. Any time. And at his convenience. Besides, any ‘sane’ person, especially sane women, would consider any other woman lucky or talented or both, who can make her husband lose his head like that” (*Changes* 12). However, Esi describes the act as marital rape, gets highly infuriated, and goes ahead to dissolve the marriage. Kate Millett makes a salient contribution to this notion as she maintains that “the concept of romantic love affords a means of emotional manipulation which the male is free to exploit, since love is the only circumstance in which the female is (ideologically) pardoned for sexual activity (37). But Esi feels differently. She is a case that Friedan describes as “unfeminine, because education, independence and equality with men have caused them to lose femininity” (27). Esi clearly controverts the image of the woman that pursues self-fulfilment through marriage and children. To her, her husband’s obsession with and demonstration of uncontrolled passion that lead to what she describes as marital rape, constitute a contravention of and infringement on her personhood, and a disregard for her rights to her sexuality. This misfeasance is a violent act within the framework of marriage.

Esi meets Ali Kondey, a Muslim who operates Linga Travel Agency. Conscious of the stereotypes that often attend African femininity, Esi carefully conducts herself at her first meeting with Ali Kondey so as not to betray her self-confidence and comportment: though he is very handsome – and he is aware that he is – “Esi was not in any mood to notice looks or be charmed by self-consciously charming men” (1); though she is tired and would like to have a drink as Ali offers her, “she was almost tempted to ask for water, at least, but she didn’t” (2); she declines his offer to drive her home, then work on her unreliable car and return it to her the next day. She

insists on driving her car, even though “the old machine [is] coughing like some asthmatic ...” (4).

That fortuitous meeting of Esi and Ali develops into a marriage, even though Ali is married to Fusena. Esi is not bothered that her mother and grandmother disapprove of her ending her marriage to Oko, and then marrying Ali. But quite different from Oko, Ali is very romantic, widely travelled and affluent in every way, and makes Esi feel his wealth. Her intense romantic relationship with Ali is because she is an emancipated woman, and according to Friedan, the “most ‘emancipated’ women, women educated beyond college for professional careers, showed a far greater capacity for complete sexual enjoyment ... than the rest ... and less likely to be frigid ... (327). However, when she feels that Ali is not giving her the time and attention she requires, she reconditions her mind to neither expect him nor seek to know his whereabouts when they are apart. Although Esi is convinced that Ali loves her deeply, what is certain is that she is not comfortable with “his fashion of loving [which] had proved quite inadequate for her” (165).

Consequently, Esi leaves the marriage, though she does not formally terminate it as she did her first marriage. Clearly, she is not a victim of any physical violation in any of her heterosexual relationships, but she is obviously a victim of emotional violence as long as the specific man she deals with can neither understand how she would like their relationship to go, nor know how to plot the configuration of his life to suit her. Her idea of femininity is in determining what she wants, and how she wants it. She feels free to terminate – formally or informally – any relationship that she finds antithetical to her ideals and expectations. By doing so, she displays her aversion to the patriarchal principle that women often desire to thrill, amuse, indulge, satiate and cajole men with their sexuality.

Chimamanda Adichie’s *Purple Hibiscus* depicts an elitist family with the father, Eugene Achike, who is an entrepreneur, an ardent philanthropist and a devout Catholic. He is widely admired and respected in the church and the society because of his frequent generous donations to individuals and groups. His wife, Beatrice Achike is a housewife and cares for their two children: Jaja (17) and Kambili (15). Known for his conspicuous religiosity, and determination to make Heaven by

surmounting all of Satan's efforts to tempt him, Eugene is overcome by an atypical steadfastness to holiness. Also, his love for his family compels him to seek that his wife and children also make Heaven at last. He feels an overwhelming responsibility to help them, guide them, and conduct them to be both successful in life and also be in eternal bliss in Heaven. In his avid commitment to save them from succumbing to the wiles and antics of Satan, he censors their activities, and imposes strict regimens on them.

Unfortunately, Eugene is so harsh and near-tyrannical towards his wife and children in his pursuit of the ideal that he gets driven into violence within the family. Having set the standards, any member of the family that falls short of his expectations risks his violent reactions. Janet Ndula elucidates that Eugene's "... spiritual conceptions combine with the entrenched traditional constructs of his home culture of Enugu to bestow him with unexamined and distorted ideologies of male superiority" (33), which he displays in diverse ways in the family. Jaja fails to go to communion during Mass on Palm Sunday, and claims that the wafer gives him bad breath, and he feels nauseated when the priest touches his mouth. These generate Eugene's lividity. He seizes the missal and hurls it across the room towards Jaja, but it rather hits and breaks Beatrice's delicate *étagère* and the ceramic figurines of ballet dancers. Beatrice silently packs away the broken pieces and cleans up the place. Another incident occurred on Christmas day as the Igwe visit Eugene's family. Beatrice greets him as tradition specifies by bending low and offering him her back so he may pat it with his traditional fan. For Eugene, that is an infraction of God's commandment in Exodus chapter 20, verse 5: "You shall not bow down to them or worship them; and "them" signifies the mundane, the temporal or the profane. Eugene complains that his wife should not have bowed to the Igwe who is a proponent of tradition, and Eugene abhors everything that is ungodly, and tradition is a prominent aspect.

Shortly after that Christmas day visit by the Igwe, Eugene and family visit the bishop in Awka, and Kambili, aware of her father's reprimand of her mother for the traditional mode of greeting that she accorded the Igwe, tries to impress him and does not kneel to kiss the bishop's ring. In a strange twist, afterwards, her father yanks her ears and indicts her for lacking discernment as she failed to accord the

bishop his deserved reverence. On the day after Christmas when Catholics observe the Eucharist fast, Kambili experiences severe menstrual pains, and she is assisted by Jaja and their mother to eat some cereal and take some panadol tablets. In reaction, Eugene gets infuriated and argues that his wife and children are on errands for the devil who may have built a tent in his (Eugene's) house. For the three of them directly or indirectly desecrating the Eucharist fast, he takes off his heavy leather belt and severely whips his wife and children, and muttering all the while that "the devil would not win" (102). When he is satisfied that he has exorcised the devil from them, he hugs Kambili and Jaja close to himself and asks them "Why do you walk into sin? Why do you sin? ... Did the belt hurt you? Did it break your skin?" (102) He actually examines them for any physical injuries.

Also, Jaja, at age 10, in his first Holy Communion class, misses two questions in his catechism test, and misses the first position. Eugene beats him up and impairs the small finger in his left hand (145). In another instance, while Kambili and Jaja are on holidays in Nsukka with Aunty Ifeoma, Eugene's father, Pa Nnukwu is also there mainly for medical attention. Eugene regards as abominable for his children to stay under the same roof with his father who is a heathen. To purge his children of the heathenish influence, he acts first on Kambili by carefully conducting her into the bathtub, and then pouring boiled water over her feet. By that cruel action Eugene seems to punish the feet that led Kambili to accede to stay in the same house with a heathen (194-5).

Furthermore, while Kambili and Jaja are on holidays in Nsukka, Eugene beats Beatrice so intensely that her face is swollen and the area around her right eye is "the black-purple shade of an overripe avocado" (190). Eugene is overwhelmed with rage as he realizes that his children returned from Nsukka with the painting of his father. Thus, to obliterate any connection between Eugene's family and Pa Nnukwu, he tears up the painting (210). In a swift reaction, Kambili dashes to the floor where the pieces of the painting are, and lies on them, and defiantly refuses to get up as her father orders her to. In desperation to save his daughter from being contaminated by the torn pieces of the painting of his father, Eugene kicks her so severely and for such a prolonged period that she is extensively injured, and all that period, he is

lamenting about the devil's destructive work in his family: "Godlessness. Heathen worship. Hellfire" (211). Kambili narrates her experience:

The stinging was raw now, even more like bites because the metal landed on open skin on my side, my back, my legs. Kicking. Kicking. Kicking. Perhaps it was a belt now because the metal buckle seemed too heavy. ...More stings. More slaps. A salty wetness warmed my mouth. I closed my eyes and slipped away into quiet (211).

And Kambili wakes to find herself in the hospital. At another time, Eugene's fury causes him to intensely batter his wife and break on her belly the small table in their lounge, which results in her excessive bleeding and loss of a 6-week old pregnancy.

Significantly, Adichie depicts in *Purple Hibiscus* a family that is brutalized and traumatized by the husband and father who is an autocratic as well as a superordinate bigot. Millet explains Eugene's intemperance and violence on his wife and children in her argument that "traditionally, patriarchy granted the father nearly total ownership over wife and children, including the power of physical abuse, and often even those of murder and sale. Classically, as head of the family, the father is both begetter and owner in a system in which kinship property" (33). In pursuit of leading a quintessential family that is also Heaven-bound, Eugene is compelled to impose his ideas on his wife and children, and to apply violence when the situation seems to become aggravated. He runs the affairs of his family and treats his wife and children with little or no empathy because of his one-dimensional mode of thinking, assessment of events in the family, and expectations of his wife and children. These make it impossible for Eugene to regard them as capable of critical thinking, and able to react to his overbearing and retrogressive lifestyle. Consequently, he continues to live in the past, and to see himself as the fulcrum on which the lives of his wife and children depend.

Responses of the Victims of Violence in the Novels

The responses of the victims of violence in the novels examined in this paper are as varied as the forms of violence and the severity of the violence that they suffer. In

fact, the histrionics of violence, as determined by the scenario of violence, impels such reactions from the victims as to guarantee each victim's survival and transcendence to a new mentality with a set of radical actions. This is what Obioma Nnaemeka implies in her argument that "extreme pain and suffering push women victims to the brink of madness" (19). It is therefore consistent that the victim's reactions are corollaries of the magnitude of their intimate male partners' insidiousness and violence. It is evident in the three novels studied in this paper that Nawal El Saadawi's varieties of violence that Firdaus experiences in *Woman at Point Zero* are different from those experienced by Beatrice in Chimamanda Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus*; and these two are at variance with the mode of violence that Esi encounters in Ama Ata Aidoo's *Changes: A Love Story*. Correspondingly, the responses of the three women are diverse and generate different consequences for the woman-victim, her image in the family, and the society, as well as her prospects.

In El Saadawi's *Woman*, Firdaus' experiences are targeted at making her a victim of deception as the omniscient narrator notes in the novel that:

All women are victims of deception. Men impose deception on women and punish them for being deceived, force them down to the lowest level and punish them for falling so low, bind them in marriage and then chastise them with menial service for life, or insults, or blows (86).

But Firdaus refuses to be deceived. She sees through the smoke screen of deception, exploitation and abuse that is erected for her by her parents, then her uncle and his wife, then Sheikh Mahmoud, who is her husband, then Bayoumi, then Sherifa, then Di'aa, then Ibrahim who disappoints her, then the police officer, and finally the pimp. In the course of her growing up, Firdaus has variously been starved of food, raped and gang-raped, mistreated, informally imprisoned, beaten up, disappointed and rejected. Subsequently, she has had to move from one location of her ordeal and adversity to another in search of better options. She recounts:

... I expect something from love. With love I began to imagine that I had become a human being ... in love I gave my body and my soul,

my mind and all the effort I could muster, freely ... in love I gave all: my capabilities, my efforts, my feelings, my deepest emotions ... (85-86).

Firdaus narrates her wasted investments while in love. While she gives everything happily and freely, she really expects nothing tangible, looks forward to no gains “except ... to be saved through love ... To find ...” (86) herself again, and to recover her humanity: not to be “looked upon with scorn, or despised, but respected and cherished and made to feel whole ...” (86). She laments the depraved society in which she finds herself, a society that derides the virtue in femininity, and never considers the woman’s quality and value. These notions effectively permeate Firdaus’ psyche. The hopelessness that she experiences makes her to confront the futility of life.

Essentially, when Marzouk, the pimp, attempts to force himself on Firdaus as her manager, and states that “every prostitute has a pimp to protect her from other pimps, and from the police ...” (92), Firdaus boldly surmounts that blackmail. Unfortunately for him, this is a changed Firdaus, a very hardened and daring lady. She declines his offer and all his negotiations; and unable to contain his vilification, she stabs him to death, and describes:

I raised the knife and buried it deep in his neck, pulled it out of his neck and then thrust it deep into his chest, pulled it out of his chest and plunged it deep into his belly. I stuck the knife into almost every part of his body. I was astonished to find how easily my hand moved as I thrust the knife into his flesh, and pulled it out almost without effort (95).

According to Patricia Collins, the essential choice for many men to protect women got evolved into ideologies of black masculinity in such a way that black manhood became dependent on black women’s willingness to accept protection. From this category of masculinity is the convergence of the protection and control of black women. This control is often obscurantist, with the aim of portraying black men as imperatively in charge. (157) Indeed, underlying the fact of the male being in charge

is the notion of power. Within the context of this study, the perspective of power is steeped in control, and it gets asphyxiating, because in the binary structure of power and powerlessness, “the power of one person is seen as depriving another of autonomy. Especially for women, the relationship to patriarchal authority is bound to be hazardous. Men have power and authority only if women’s equality is denied” (189). The dialectics of power, authority and control manifest in the subjugation of the woman in any form of relationship in the three novels. After murdering the pimp, Firdaus in El Saadawi’s *Woman* attains the peak of her psychological liberation, chutzpah and audaciousness.

In Adichie’s *Purple Hibiscus*, Beatrice responds in a similar way to the atrociousness and brutality that Eugene frequently displays towards his family members. After the years of enduring a marriage in which she has been treated with debasement by her husband, Beatrice murders him by slowly poisoning his tea. She confesses “I started putting the poison in his tea before I came to Nsukka. Sisi [the family’s housekeeper] got it for me; her uncle is a powerful witch doctor” (290). However, Jaja claims that he poisoned his father, and it is much easier for the policemen to believe that Jaja did the act, rather than Beatrice. By taking responsibility of Eugene’s death, Jaja indirectly provides a covering for his mother and his sister; and his willingness to go to jail serves as an alibi and a redemptive role for his mother who actually committed the crime. Thus, the children identify and share with their mother in the act of the murder of their father. This corporate obligation, therefore, is a guarantee for their freedom, and ultimately a harmonious future for them all.

Ama Ata Aidoo introduces a distinct form of violence in *Changes* to which Esi responds, not by taking life to protect herself, but by acting in an equally obnoxious manner. The context of violence that Esi experiences is emotional. Clearly, sexual violence is a locus where patriarchal oppressions and traumas intersect. It also methodically denotes the bipartite myths of the typical black man as hopelessly bestial, a feature that the black woman should be conscious of and avoid tempting him. The next is the myth of the black woman as a pornographic object, and a helplessly sexualized entity that is consequently responsible for her own victimization by the rapist. Esi is vibrant, well educated, ambitious and alluring. She

makes money just as her male counterparts, and reasonably more than her husband. But she is seen as frustrated and 'masculinized' by her career. She accuses her husband of marital rape, and feels unable to contain the trauma from that violation, and subsequently terminates the marriage. She also suffers emotional contusion in her second marriage to Ali Kondey who does not accord her adequate attention and physical presence. Thus, she walks out of the marriage.

Obviously, the three women – Firdaus, Esi and Beatrice – are samples of Phauual Egejuru's notion of womanself. According to her, "distinctive feature of womanself is the ability to choose and act upon its choices. Because society is used to womanbeing that should not and does not choose, it inaccurately sees womanself as rebellious (5). For the intimate partners of these women, Edgar Nabutanyi highlights that "the enactment of violence to enforce publicly visible religious piety devalues one of the core aspects of Catholicism: the centrality of a happy family. The unhappiness of this family because of Eugene's seriously unbalanced personality is poignantly depicted in ..." (78) the several acts of assault that he unleashes on his wife and children in Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus*. The same principle applies in the evaluation of Sheikh Mahmoud's personality as a renowned religious leader, but who brutalizes the young Firdaus who is unfortunate to be his wife. That the three women studied in this paper as victims of violence in love relationships, take action against their assailants is a proof of El Saadawi's conception in *The Hidden Face of Eve* that "action is an essential element of love ... [and that] romantic love sustains itself through deprivation ..." (77). While the three women in romantic love contexts are deprived of the privilege of choice, Firdaus in *Woman* is further deprived of a credible and respectable life; Esi in *Changes* is deprived of the prerogative of giving prominence to her career and then fitting in family as she deems fit; and in *Purple Hibiscus*, Beatrice is deprived of peace and harmony in the family for the healthy growth of her children, Jaja and Kambili. Indeed, the responses of the women are evidence that every assaulted woman owes herself the obligation of reacting to save herself, her potentialities, her children (if any), her career, her future, her posterity, and more. Thus, even if not for themselves, Firdaus, Esi and Beatrice respond to violence as a way of setting templates for a better future for women in such circumstances.

Conclusion

When El Saadawi tells Firdaus through the pimp in *Woman at Point Zero* that “you’re living an illusion. I can see in your eyes how love has broken the spirit that used to shine” (93), she is challenging every African woman in an intimate relationship to be conscious of possible abuses, assaults and debauchery. Nana, Esi’s grandmother in Aidoo’s *Changes* reiterates El Saadawi’s opinion above by telling Esi to “... remember that a man always gains in stature any way he chooses to associate with a woman – including adultery ... But in her association with a man, a woman is always in danger of being diminished (164). She sounds the need for the woman to look critically and identify the deception of the intimate male partner that constitutes a shield for the violence by cheating, denigration, exploitation and vilipending of the woman.

Significantly, this study both appraises these realities as well as the diverse manifestations and reactions of the woman victim in each circumstance. Though the women’s responses are radical, Obioma Nnaemeka contends that what is radical in the three women’s reactions to their experiences of abuse is not so much what they did (murder) but how it was done (intentionality). The women’s radical reactions are consequences of the relationship between awareness and madness, which leads to a search for freedom, and freedom here, is conceived as not just to liberate self, but to obliterate the agent of bondage. Invariably, what is noteworthy is not so much the fact that the women concerned are mad but how they utilize their madness (19). Specifically, as far as Firdaus is concerned, the typical man is a criminal: “all of you: the fathers, the uncles, the husbands, the pimps, the lawyers, the doctors, the journalists, and all men of all professions” (*Woman* 100). El Saadawi, Aidoo and Adichie portray women who demonstrate advancement beyond Nnu Ego in Buchi Emecheta’s *The Joys of Motherhood* whose conviction is that her humanity becomes concrete and total through motherhood. Yet rather than experience the joys there from, she suffers from motherhood, lives in misery because she (and her husband, Nnaife) can hardly afford the requirements to meet the needs of the large family; then she dies despicably by the road side amidst abject poverty, loneliness and contempt.

Contemporary realities indicate that femininity should be a concept that is not subject to torture in the milieu of passion; whether in marriage or not, the woman does not deserve to be violated. The different responses of Firdaus, Esi and Beatrice prove that modern women recognize that they have choices, and that their choices should prominently ensure self-preservation. The utmost value and the only commitment for modern women is the fulfillment of their own femininity. The greatest error that people make has been the undervaluation of femininity. Freidan notes that femininity is so mysterious and intuitive and close to creation and origin of life that man-made science may never be able to understand it. Though different, it must never be regarded as inferior to the nature of men (43). This study's discourse on choices recognizes the essence of Phaniel Egejuru's opinion on womanbeing and womanself. According to her, although Womanbeing is created, exploited and ruled by society, there comes a time when the self within the being rebels and emerges to reclaim its own separate identity from being. Thus, Womanself could be defined as a state of freedom arising out of liberation from the shackles of Womanbeing. In other words, Womanself emerges in reaction to societies' rules and impositions of Womanbeing (4). The three women studies in this paper reveal that unlike their foremothers including Efuru in Flora Nwapa's novel by the same title, Emecheta's Nnu Ego in *The Joys of Motherhood*, Ramatoulaye in Mariama Ba's *So Long a Letter*, Beauty in Sindiwe Magona's *Beauty's Gift* and others, prevailing factors impel them to call into question the place and role of the woman in patriarchy, and jettison the image of the archetypal underdog, whose victimhood status is gender-determined.

Importantly, Ada Azodo asserts that the patriarchal system sets up men and women from the early developmental stages of childhood with the idea that gender differences are necessarily signs of inferiority and superiority. It teaches that female is weak and inferior and male is strong and superior. It also teaches men to dominate, and women to be subservient and submissive ...” (53). Patriarchy typically links feeling of cruelty with sexuality, the latter often equated both with evil and with power. The rule here associates sadism with the male (“the masculine role”) and victimization with the female (“the feminine role”) (Millett 44). Phaniel Egejuru extends this notion in her contention that:

Whereas society expects and encourages man's self to emerge and flourish, society does everything in its power, not only to discourage the emergence of woman's self, it also tries to smother and destroy woman's self if it emerged (4-5).

The diverse responses of the three women to the violent acts on them in intimate relationships constitute a signification of their protest against the devalorisation of femininity, which should be checked in modern societies, and that check has to be undertaken by women. That is the stage that women attain selfhood, which Egejuru elucidates in her metaphoric treatise, *Womanbeing and Womanself* that "Self is innate but is encased within Being. It takes an individual's will power to liberate her self from her being. ... Emerging from being to self is completely dependent upon human will (187, 188). The roles of Firdaus, Esi and Beatrice in the novels under study in this paper pave the way for according humanity, vitality and authenticity to women.

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